

Trying to Understand the Psychology of Guilt?

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 6, No. 6-01, 2024, p. 01 - 36. - 0099-0001-2401-0301.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")
ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with

Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE
("Scientific Studies - Current

CURRENT SCIENCE

Science Georgia”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) Science Georgia”) journal with a multi-science peer-review.” (“Scientific Studies - Current Science

Georgia”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

““The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.”“ (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this (“Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia”)

““• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.”“ (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

**Author(s) Name and Surname: Dr. Clinical Psychologist
Melis Avci (0009-0009-2241-8049)**

University: St Clements University

Department: Clinical Psychology

Title: Dr. Clinical Psychologist

Date: January 2024

Abstract

A human is characterized as a social entity. Nevertheless, it is evident that individuals sometimes exhibit behaviors that are in opposition to societal norms, with certain individuals adopting this as a habitual pattern and displaying a detrimental disposition towards the established social structure. These criminal behaviors manifest within small, informal groups based on the internal regulations of said groups, while larger institutions and governmental bodies enforce their own rules, regulations, and laws. In society, efforts are made to manage such behaviors through

conventional methods like condemnation, ostracism, or punishment. Each of these social control systems enforces penalties on individuals who breach social norms (Binder, 1988). On one side, efforts are made to regulate crime via the deterrent of laws. On the other hand, researchers are investigating the biological, social, and psychological factors that contribute to crime, as well as exploring methods of prevention. Researchers specializing in criminology have proposed several ideas to explain criminal behavior. Each of these hypotheses, although valuable in enhancing our comprehension of the issue, lacks individual adequacy in explaining the crime. Eisenberg and Patterson (1979) contend that it is erroneous to categorize all offenders under a single category and advocate for the establishment of several groups based on different characteristics.

**Keywords: Guilt, Guilt Psychology,
Psychology, Human Psychology, Causes of
Guilt as Psychological**

Introduction

Guilt is a composite of conduct, emotion, and thinking, and it represents a kind of subjective encounter. It refers to the subjective encounters inside an individual's mind that influence their actions towards themselves or others. This introspective process involves self-reflection on one's actions and contemplation of negative aspects. (Sıgırıcı et al., 2010). Hence, it is crucial to recognize that guilt should not be just regarded as an affective condition. The Dictionary of Psychology (Karakas, 2018) defines emotion as the manifestation of feelings resulting from significant individual events and factors, including physiological, behavioral, and experiential aspects. Guilt may be assessed from an emotional standpoint, resulting in a subjective sensation of guilt. However, when guilt is examined from a cognitive and behavioral perspective, it manifests as an experiential state of guilt. Guilt is rooted on scientific principles and arises via numerous cognitive processes and behavioral manifestations of an individual. The individual's self-structure encompasses their awareness of a situation, as well as their attitudes, knowledge, talents, and experiences pertaining to that scenario.

The only way to alleviate the guilt stemming from negative experiences in relationships or situations caused by events that have adverse effects on individuals is by rectifying the behaviors that contribute to the individual's negative emotions. Nevertheless, when an incident occurs that directly affects the person, their subsequent conduct towards themselves due to the guilt they experience becomes a noteworthy worry throughout the process. Guilt arises from improper conduct and serves as a reaction to reinforce adherence to established norms, so promoting the continuation of social conduct within a certain framework. Guilt, as an emotion, incurs costs for both the person and society (Karatas, 2008).

A crime is an act that is banned by law and may result in legal consequences if committed or disregarded. The individual who commits such a crime is referred to as a criminal. Engaging in aggressive activities that violate societal rules initiates criminal behavior, which becomes evident when the assault is directed at its primary target. Upon the discovery of a crime, a punitive measure is enforced onto the perpetrator, and a Penal Code is established to deter the occurrence of criminal activities. Crime has a framework that seeks to undermine the established social hierarchy, regardless of the extent to which it infringes upon individual rights. Crime has been around from the inception of humanity and has persisted throughout history. The composition of the criminal element is influenced by the economic, social, and spiritual prospects available within a community.

In sociology, socialization is the primary process by which an individual develops a personality that aligns with the advantages of their social culture. Social culture encompasses the collective habits, traditions, and norms of a particular group to which the individual belongs. Reward and punishment are crucial elements in the process of socialization. Religious precepts also include crime within their scope. Behaviors that generate negativity in the surroundings are seen as sins and in opposition to the divine intentions. Cesare Beccaria's treatise "On Crimes and Punishments", published in 1764, approached the topic of crime from a scientific perspective, influenced by rationality and Enlightenment philosophy. Key factors to be taken into account include the constitutional rules governing criminal procedures, the idea of individual accountability, the notion that criminal behavior is a product of personal will, and the psychological aspects involved in the commission of a crime. In the late 20th century and early 21st century, it was assessed and analyzed using a "Guilty Predominant" perspective based on Positivist Theory. In his 1876 publication "Criminal Person," Lombroso conducted an analysis of

the psychological, sociological, and physiological traits of criminals. He emphasized the significance of assessing the level of danger posed by criminals and advocated for the utilization of suitable methodologies in this determination.

The post-World War II perspective explored the notion of causality in the components of criminal activity and analyzed the overall dynamic between the offender and the victim as a social interaction occurring within the context of their shared environment. Evaluating the causation process should be done in two distinct steps.

a) Social Process refers to the influence of the social environment on an individual's behavior. b) Individual Process refers to the connections that develop between the guilty person and their families, particularly the relationship between the guilty person and the victim.

Various concepts, such as Genetic Determinism, Social Environment Effects, Personality Theories, and Situational and Environmental Determinism, are significant frameworks to explore while considering the causes of crime. The overarching framework that encompasses all these schools is the Pluralistic Theory of Guilt.

The amalgamation of fundamental principles such as science, art, morality, and justice have significant importance in the context of embodying a contemporary individual. Justice and morality are intricately linked to culpability and occupy the highest position in the hierarchy, although they lack a distinct and unequivocal essence. Hence, it might vary throughout different societies.

The failure to fulfill an individual's fundamental physiological requirements, coupled with a lack of affection or respect, has a detrimental impact on their motivation towards various events and circumstances. This leads to uncertainty within their living environment and subsequently increases their inclination towards criminal behavior. By engaging in illicit circumstances, the person subdues the perception of criminality prior to carrying out an unlawful action. Individuals who have not developed a stable and healthy sense of identity during their upbringing exhibit excessive and aggressive behavior in order to easily fulfill their unmet instincts, desires, and expectations. These individuals are unable to find stability due to the pressures of their surroundings, leading them to view criminal actions as a potential solution. Three psychological aspects that contribute to the prevalence of crime, in addition to socio-economic problems, may be identified as follows:

1-The "overly simple solution" response is one of the defensive mechanisms that individuals use to cope with the overwhelming stimulus caused by fast change.

2- The preference for this option is due to an aggressive and authoritarian mentality, despite the presence of several defensive systems against overstimulation.

3- Response to the abrupt psychological and social transformation

The psychological traits of an individual have a significant role in shaping criminal behavior. As such, no social aspect is regarded to be a standalone cause of crime.

The public exhibits significant interest in news about crimes due to the prevailing inclination of people to oppose the occurrences inside society. The

heroes are also given this attention. The criminal and hero typology delineates two distinct manifestations of bravery shown by individuals when confronted with perilous circumstances. In this scenario, the culpable individual faces a perilous predicament, while the courageous one defies an imminent peril. Psychologists argue that crime is an outward manifestation of suppressed emotions in individuals. Thus, people develop a fascination with those who possess qualities that resonate with their inner desires, ultimately fulfilling their violent tendencies. Meninger describes crime as a universal allure. According to Maslow, one of the primary needs of individuals is the desire for equilibrium, in addition to a sense of safety and security. These are accomplished in conjunction with the environmental mandate. Conversely, crime has a detrimental impact on the organization of the environment and incites our sense of self-importance. From this viewpoint, crime might be compared to a persistent force that hinders the favorable trajectory of our life.

Crime instills dread and has a detrimental impact on social life, causing disruptions in interpersonal connections. Consequently, the individual experiences a lack of safety, grapples with various psychological issues, and faces social adversities.

Examining the occurrence of crime is crucial for comprehending human behavior. Individuals are often seen as either adhering to or deviating from standards. Understanding the reasons for individual deviations from these standards is crucial for comprehending their actions.

Benefits of addressing guilt:

1-The modus operandi used by the culpable individual to address and resolve issues enables the identification of crucial factors in crime prevention, judicial procedures, and the assessment of criminal elements.

Crime serves as a means to get insights on the social and cultural possibilities and belief systems prevalent in a certain community.

To get insights into the cognitive framework of a criminal person, it is insufficient to only analyze the action itself. The element of crime encompasses not only the actions of the individual who commits the crime, but also the many elements that contribute to the occurrence of the crime. While two criminal components may seem identical in their compliance with societal norms and legal regulations, their psychological profiles might vary significantly due to distinct traits.

Neurobiology of Guilt

The current understanding of the influence of mixed emotions on the brain, which underlies social and moral actions, remains incomplete (Wagner et al., 2011). Furthermore, investigating the brain characteristics of moral emotions will provide insights into the neuronal frameworks underlying acts deemed immoral in individuals with mental and neurological disorders. A key characteristic of psychopathy is the lack of regret and guilt. The references used are Hare (1991) and Lykken (1995).

Several studies have shown that shame and guilt elicit activity in shared regions of the brain, such as the prefrontal cortex. However, other research has identified interactions occurring at distinct locations within the brain.

Takahashi et al. (2004) performed research to identify the specific brain region where the sense of guilt is associated, using the fMRI technique. Initially, the participants were instructed to assess the aforementioned lines, which were deliberately crafted as neutral statements that may potentially induce feelings

of guilt. Selected were statements that effectively elicited sentiments of guilt, which were then presented alongside neutral words to the subjects during the brain imaging procedure. The study findings indicate that the ventromedial prefrontal cortex (VMPFC), the left posterior superior temporal sulcus (STS), and the visual cortex are the specific regions of the brain that engage with guilt-inducing words (Takahashi et al., 2004).

Prior research has also shown that the ventromedial prefrontal cortex (VMPFC) plays a crucial role in assessing both individual and collective mental attributes (Castelli, Happé, Frith, & Frith, 2000; Frith & Frith, 2001), as well as in the realm of moral judgment. The references used are Greene et al. (2001) and Heekeren, Wartenburger, Schmidt, Schwintowski, and Villringer (2003).

Separate research conducted a more comprehensive analysis of the role of guilt in the prefrontal cortex. The participants in this study on the act of guilt were provided with keywords that pertain to the particular experiences of those involved in the Imri incident. Thus, other investigations opted for a distinct approach whereby the aim was to elicit emotions of guilt in the participants by using their autobiographical recollections. The imaging analysis demonstrated that guilt was primarily associated with activation in the right orbitofrontal cortex and paracingulate dorsomedial prefrontal cortex regions of the prefrontal cortex. However, no significant effects were seen for emotions of shame and dissatisfaction (Wagner et al., 2011). Additionally, there was a need to assess the participants of this research based on the level of guilt noticed in their autobiographical recollections. The study found that there was a direct correlation between the participants' guilt levels and the activity in the right orbitofrontal cortex (Wagner et al., 2011).

Empirical research demonstrates that the ventromedial prefrontal cortex (VMPFC) and orbitofrontal cortex (OFC) play a crucial role in regulating social behavior. Individuals who have dysfunctions in the orbitofrontal cortex (OFC) and ventromedial prefrontal cortex (VMPFC), as well as developmental brain abnormalities resulting from external injury, have been reported to exhibit insensitivity to social norms and engage in psychopathic and antisocial behaviors (Anderson et al., 1999; Blair, 2007; Yang and Raine, 2009).

Research conducted by Shin et al. (2000) used PET imaging instead of fMRI to investigate specific brain regions that are involved in the sense of guilt but not influenced by neutral emotions. The paralimbic regions identified in the study include the anterior cingulate fold, temporal pole, frontal fold, and insula fold. According to research, both the anterior cingulate and insula regions are involved in perceiving displays of disgust and experiencing the sense of disgust. Additionally, these regions are also responsible for responding to and understanding witnessed pain. The significance of these two emotions in comprehending others and attaining insight has been noted (Bernhardt and Singer, 2012; Decety and Jackson, 2004). It may be inferred that the exchanges about guilt at these moments are also linked to seeing one's own errors from the perspective of others and evaluating the damage inflicted on others. The strong anatomical connections between the insula, temporal pole, prefrontal cortex, OFC, amygdala, and anterior cingulate cortex are consistent with their shared functions in regulating comparable emotions and facilitating interaction (Bernhardt and Singer, 2012).

Current structural brain analyses pertaining to crime are inadequate. Given that the brain operates on the principle of "use it or lose it" and research on brain plasticity indicates that the areas of the brain that are used will undergo

structural growth, it is reasonable to infer that studies on the structure of the brain may provide valuable insights into the nature of these distinct emotions.

METHODS IN THE PSYCHOLOGY OF GUILT

1 - **Experimental Method:** The experimenter passively watches and patiently awaits the occurrence of a circumstance. The copious amount of information acquired via the experimental technique serves as a safeguard against misinterpretations stemming from subjective inquiries.

Behaviorism, spearheaded by Watson, examines how actions are influenced by the social and physical environment, as well as the physiological capabilities of the body. This perspective also contributes significantly to the study of guilt in psychology. Hence, it is customary to get an objective outcome without considering the subjective assertions of the culpable individual or the witness.

The endorsement of Gestalt Psychology and Psychoanalysis, both of which fully embrace the concept of personality, for Guilt Psychology is readily apparent. Willpower, awareness, and absence of awareness play a significant role in guilt. Furthermore, it is widely acknowledged that Adler's guilt led to the commission of several criminal acts.

2- **Introspection Method:** Subjective psychology relies on the technique of observing, assessing, and drawing conclusions about an individual's internal experiences. Introspection reveals reasonable insights into the mind and psychological processes. Despite facing significant criticism, this approach effectively examines the psychological framework of criminal behavior via the

use of survey methodology. Prior to asserting the total accuracy of the data, it is crucial to carefully monitor and analyze the conduct of the culpable individual both during and after the incident.

The Psychopathological approach, an important compendium in the field of guilt psychology, seeks to comprehend the significance of the interplay between mental disorders and guilt.

The scope of criminal psychology should be delineated in a comprehensive manner. External factors have an impact on criminal behavior, in addition to the psychological condition of the person. Upon examination, social facts assume a characteristic that impacts the psychological makeup of an individual after a psychological transformation.

Abnormal conduct and criminal behavior have many similarities. The research conducted within these two categories mostly focus on persons confined in jails and hospitals, whose lives have been constrained at certain junctures. Examinations conducted on imprisoned persons provide insights into the underlying causes of criminal behavior, as well as the evaluation of the efficacy of laws and punishment strategies, and the impact of institutions on criminal conduct.

While addressing the issue of guilt, it is crucial to examine the harmonious integration of the whole personality as well as the interconnectedness of various aspects of the problem.

An investigation is conducted on the disharmony in mental structure, specifically focusing on the changes between abstract and concrete tests, accomplishment and performance exams, and various mental talents.

2-Socio-cultural structure: The conflict arises when individuals fail to adhere to the conventions, traditions, and rules of the social society. For instance, behaviors such as fraud, murder, and the usurpation of someone else's property.

3- Temperamental dissonance: This refers to the investigation of the conflicting qualities that develop from the tension between repressed and forgotten emotional experiences and more recent ones in mental conflicts.

4- Incompatibility in somatic structure: This section examines the relationship between somatic dysfunctions and morphological structure. The physical characteristics of people, including both criminals and non-criminals, are used as criterion. One of the objectives of somatic and medical examination is to identify the disparities in temperament and behavior between those who are unwell and those who are innocent, based on the premise that poor health has an impact on these aspects.

Criminology is an interdisciplinary field that examines the underlying causes and mechanisms of crime, including biological and social factors, via the use of experimental methodologies to study the characteristics of criminal individuals. All behaviors classified as "deviant" are significant in the field of Criminology.

Deviant Behaviors (Deviance)

The term "deviation" is derived from the verb "to deviate" and refers to atypical, abnormal, and uncommon behaviors. Deviant conduct refers to actions that violate societal norms and expectations, such as immoral behavior,

violence, adultery, prostitution, homosexuality, excessive gambling, and perversion.

Criminals can generally be interpreted into three groups:

1- Those who have acquired the habit of committing crime: This category includes individuals who have aggressive tendencies, lack emotional responsiveness, struggle to adjust to their surroundings, demonstrate a distortion of their natural instincts, and present a challenging and resistant risk, such as those who are addicted to drugs and alcohol.

2- Those who commit crimes accidentally: Individuals who engage in criminal activities while under the sway of emotions such as agony, abrupt rage, and envy, are included under this category due to the indoctrination and influence exerted by society and another person. This group includes persons referred to as "debilitates," who possess limited intelligence and capabilities, and are compelled by the person in authority to participate in a negative scenario. Additionally, it comprises impulsive individuals known as "impulsives," individuals driven by a desire for vengeance, and those who have jealousy towards one another.

3-Mental patients who commit crimes : These individuals include those who are unaware in their behavior, suffer from a severe mental disorder that impairs their ability to behave sensibly, and engage in criminal activities that align with the repercussions of their mental disease. These individuals are not subjected to punishment as a kind of penalty; rather, they are provided with therapy and rehabilitation at a mental illness treatment facility.

The leading figures of the classical school, which was built on **hedonistic psychology, were Beccaria and Jeremy Bentham**. Hedonistic belief governs an individual's conduct based on the experience of pain and pleasure. The anticipated pleasure derived from a certain activity is weighed against the expected suffering resulting from the same behavior. At this juncture, the individual will be predisposed to engage in this conduct, since the gratification derived from defying the law outweighs the resulting discomfort. Bentham's criminal consequence should be designed to effectively deter those who have committed crimes from engaging in more impactful criminal activities upon their release. Beccaria argues that all individuals who commit crimes should receive uniform criminal penalties, irrespective of their physical well-being, age, or social standing. At this juncture, there ought to exist a state of concordance between the act of punishment and the offense committed. Ferri argues that crime is the culmination of several factors converging into a single moment. The elements include location of residence, race, climate and temperature, as well as material, social, and anthropological aspects. Social customs include several aspects such as religion, economic realities, and population density. Garofalo is another individual who shares similar thoughts to Lombro. These two individuals assert the significance of focusing on the investigation of culpable persons rather than the crime in se. However, in contrast to Lombroso, Garofalo exercised prudence when considering genetics, asserting that criminality was determined by one's psychological disposition. Garofalo underscores the need of isolating the criminal person from their surrounding environment. Hooton (1939), based on extensive study conducted over a period of 12 years in America, asserts that non-social movements are influenced by racial and physical factors.

Marxist and socialist ideologies originated from a deterministic perspective that regards the criminal element as a result of both direct and indirect influences of capitalist-socioeconomic chances. Montesquieu, in his book *Laws*, asserts that there is a positive correlation between the murder rate and proximity to the Equator, and a positive correlation between drunkenness and proximity to the poles. Quetelet further posited that homicides are more prevalent in regions with hotter climates and nations where hot seasons are more frequent, while property-related offenses are more prevalent in regions with colder climates and countries where cold seasons are more frequent. Nevertheless, he conceptualized guilt as the principle governing thermal energy. Verkko asserts that incidents against individuals' lives increase throughout the summer season, whereas incidents targeting individuals' possessions intensify during the winter season. Sheldon Glueck argues that the occurrence of criminal behavior cannot be solely attributed to morally and economically devastated communities, since there are many youngsters who do not engage in criminal activity in these locations. The environment and culture exert influence on the persons living in that particular setting. To comprehend culture, it is necessary to possess information about the disposition and physical makeup of the person. Lacassagne (1843-1924) is credited with establishing the field of Criminal Anthropology and Criminal Sciences. He also served as a Professor of Forensic Medicine. Lacassagne discusses the crucial aspects of social society in relation to the behavior of criminal persons. The author asserts that the environment plays a significant role in inciting criminal activities and facilitating the expression of dormant and asocial impulses. Lacassagne posits his idea as follows: The social milieu, the context in which criminal behavior takes place, serves as a cultural instrument for crime. The impact of individual traits on the incidence of criminal activity is a significant aspect. Nevertheless, this scenario has little

significance and yields a subordinate impact. The germ is the main cause, and the significance of the person lies only in their ability to locate a suitable host to infect. According to Lacassagne, society possess criminals that are commensurate with their own merits. According to Aristotle's assertion, "Every nation receives the government it merits." Sykes attempted to analyze the origins of crimes by examining three aspects of the ideas. These include societal ideals, societal norms, and societal institutions.

Travis Hirschi identifies three fundamental sociological perspectives on the origins of crime:

1-Tension and Motivational Theories: This theory is sometimes referred to as the disparity of opportunity. Individuals experiencing stress disregard middle-class ideas and adopt non-social beliefs.

In this alternative approach, control theory highlights the significance of acquired inhibitions in preventing crime. This theory raises inquiries about the mechanisms and processes via which social integration takes place and is established.

The cultural deviation hypothesis emphasizes the role of learning and posits that persons who engage in criminal behavior acquire their values and beliefs from other individuals involved in illegal activities, rather than from law-abiding individuals.

His words to the French Sociologist Emile Durkheim led to the sensation of anomie, which in turn leads to repercussions such as crime and suicide. Merton conducted an examination of this notion. Merton argues that unmet wants and needs lead to deviant conduct in people, as well as a lack of adherence to the prevailing moral standards in their surroundings, known as anomie. Cloward

and Ohlin's Contrarian Opportunities Theory addresses the challenges confronted by those experiencing low levels of stress. The inclination to own commodities, the pursuit of affluence, and the societal framework stimulate fervor and cravings. When legal options are obstructed, individuals tend to resort to using illicit means, leading to the emergence of criminal activities. Many individuals believe that the occurrence of criminal activity may be mitigated by expanding legal avenues, particularly for youthful offenders.

According to Cohen's Reaction Theory, individuals who are young, have low income, and belong to the middle class, may engage in criminal behavior as a result of their inability to attain the necessary socialization and social status required to achieve their goals. This is attributed to the feelings of depression and frustration that arise from their perceived exclusion from middle-class norms. These crimes are often detrimental, characterized by negative traits, and committed with malicious intent.

Based on the conflict model:

1- Social conflict is a pervasive phenomenon in all societies, occurring consistently.

2- Every culture experiences several inevitable changes throughout time.

All societal groupings universally endorse the process of change that occurs throughout time.

4- Every civilization is established based on the premise that some individuals limit their principles.

George Vold was the first Criminologist to assert that crime is a consequence of social interaction, reflecting social and political disparities. In his 1886

remark, Gabriel Tarde introduced the concept of an intermediate mechanism that emphasizes the role of the social environment in the development of criminal conduct, challenging the notion that criminal tendencies are solely congenital. Tarde argues that imitation is a psychological aspect and a process that plays a role in vital activities. He identifies destructiveness, hierarchical pattern, and structure as the guiding principles for imitation approaches.

Thorsten Sellin (1938) is a prominent scholar who extensively explores and elucidates the notion of cultural conflict, providing the most comprehensive and insightful analysis of this concept. According to this approach, criminal law may be defined as the conduct shown by a certain segment of society. When an individual's cultural norms align with an act that the dominant culture considers unacceptable, it creates a conducive climate for a criminal occurrence to take place.

Ferreuci and Wolfgang discuss a subculture that is associated with the presence of this particular kind of violence. Taft argues that crime is a result of social interactions, institutions, and value systems, as well as past and present experiences, which include many attitudes and behaviors. According to Tannebaum, culture is the collective result of the intersection between criminal behavior and societal norms.

As per Sutherland's statement,

1- Criminal conduct is learned by association with diverse individuals at opportune moments.

2- The acquisition of criminal conduct occurred at a later time.

3- Studying criminal conduct

4- It demonstrates variations in the length of differences, frequency of connection, hierarchy of importance, and level of intensity.

5- The legal definitions indicate that impulses may or may not be deemed acceptable based on their own trajectory.

6- While criminal conduct may stem from general wants and values, it cannot be solely attributed to them, since activities that are not deemed criminal may also arise from the same needs and values.

7- Comprehending criminal conduct has resemblance to other forms of learning. Within this particular framework, the acquisition of illegal conduct is not just confined to imitation.

According to Hans Eysenck, individuals have an innate inclination to seek pleasure and avoid the experience of suffering. When discussing the equilibrium between pleasure and pain, it is necessary to examine several factors. The outcome that is most proximate to the action in terms of time has higher significance and exerts a stronger influence, particularly with regards to pain and pleasure. The initial enjoyment of a minor pleasure leads to the repetition of the behavior, regardless of the subsequent severely unpleasant consequences. The detrimental characteristics of this circumstance diminish as the duration between the occurrence of the offense and the implementation of punishment lengthens. Eysenck demonstrates that the crime phenomenon actively seeks immediate pleasure and gratification. Eysenck argues that the development of supplementary approaches for criminal penalties is a significant matter. Due to the temporal correlation between the penalty and the action, as well as the absence of any circumstances for punishment, the punishment will not be in effect. According to Eysenck's view, this scenario should prompt the emergence of conscience. Eysenck's concept of conscience

has resemblance to Freud's superego discourse and plays a crucial role in crime prevention and the identification of its underlying causes.

In contrast, Newcomb (1950) contends that the connections between an individual's identity and reference groups are responsible for criminal behavior. When the reference group of a person finds it challenging to achieve contentment, many approaches arise. According to the concept of Social and Symbolic Interaction, human motions may be understood as the result of social interactions between individuals. Personality and cognition are not inherent attributes of a person, but rather a result of the societal environment in which they reside. Symbolization and communication include the process of individuals elucidating both the identities of others and their own. Currently, the ambiguity and subjective character of social interactions, together with the multitude of societal roles, contribute to the challenges of "deviation" and play a crucial part in delineating illegal behavior. There is no absolute, universal principles that govern human conduct.

Howard Becker argues that aberrant conduct is a product of the social groupings themselves. While some social organizations establish and enforce the aforementioned groupings, they portray them as being separate from society, or in other words, outside of it. Individuals who engage in aberrant behavior are classified as criminals and deviants just upon being apprehended. Once an individual is apprehended and officially labeled as a criminal, their immediate surroundings see a notable change in their demeanor. Consequently, that individual has now established a position for themselves in an alternative social standing.

Stamp is a novel written by Reşat Nuri Güntekin that portrays the transformation of a protagonist who is unjustly accused of theft while trying to

protect the honor of his beloved. As a result, he gradually descends into moral corruption and alienation, exploring the consequences of his actions and their connection to specific transactions.

According to Shahom, social deviance is mostly caused by stigmatization and the stigma system. Considering this concept, guilt and deviance manifest as a social stigma, whereby the individual internalizes and assimilates the labels attributed to them as an integral part of their own identity. The social and cultural potential, as well as the financial advantages, of a person are diminished by the stigma associated with their sexual orientation, political beliefs, or criminal record. Thus, the position and standing of the individual within the social milieu undergoes transformation. Currently, the society itself generates deviance and guilt through the interplay among social groupings. It is customary to categorize humans in the living world into two distinct groups.

1- Individuals who conform to established standards, particularly those who engage in censorship

2- Individuals that experience social response or social repulsion, meaning they are subjected to censorship.

Stigmatization has the capacity to deter those who break from societal norms and prospective offenders, rather than only punishing them. Given that the person is impacted by the fear of stigmatization, criminal punishment has a unique position when it comes to recommendations. The person is concerned about the potential loss of his social standing, his existing employment and reputation, and the prospect of being socially isolated. Stigma is a crucial and significant factor in adhering to societal standards.

Stamping serves a dual purpose:

1- The order of society is maintained and protected by the negative feedback mechanism, which discourages individuals with a well-developed superego and social status from acting in ways that go against societal standards.

2- Restricting the access of former criminals to the environment as a consequence of their criminal conviction (positive feedback). The stigmatized individual undermines their self-esteem equilibrium by the use of positive reinforcement, and then attains a new social standing through the bestowed label.

Lemert outlines the trajectory that leads to criminal deviation in the following manner:

1- Initial deviation

2-Socially Imposed Sanctions

3-Recurring Deviation

4-Stricter forms of penalties and prohibitions

5- Recurrence and animosity towards those enforcing punishments

6-The environment marginalizes the nonconforming person

Deviant behavior experiences a rise in frequency and intensifies.

8- Embracing an Unconventional Social Position and Striving to Adjust to this Role

Deviation ultimately leads to the stigmatized person internalizing this identity after experiencing a series of oscillations. Lemert acknowledges this condition as a kind of defensive and adaptive mechanism. Consequently, there is a surge

in criminal activity. Stamping activities are essential for the operation of society. Contrastingly, a society characterized by severe judgment of all activities is shown as a scenario of expenditure.

Sociological theories aim to elucidate feelings of guilt based on the time of acquisition of knowledge. Those who advocate for this condition get advantages from the fundamental principles of psychology pertaining to the acquisition of information. Certain individuals exhibit biological motions that are governed by innate instincts, reflexes, and impulses. Furthermore, some habits manifest as a result of ongoing learning experiences throughout an individual's lifespan. To acquire information effectively, it is crucial for the person to demonstrate a willingness to adequately prepare for a given circumstance and adapt to its demands. Behavior, attitude, and functional preparedness all refer to the interior mental condition of a person. Family, social groups, and educational institutions have played a crucial role in shaping the learning process from early infancy. Nevertheless, it has an influence on learning by providing validating or disproving instances.

According to Healy, personality disorders are the fundamental basis of people' conduct. Furthermore, he said that crimes often include disorders of excitement and that individuals may only satisfy their desires by engaging in activities that involve illegal behavior. Freud posited that the id, ego, and superego are three fundamental components that must maintain equilibrium with one another. He said that every individual has a domain and signifies a certain objective. According to the psychoanalytic approach, crime is believed to occur when the internal mechanisms of self-control are unable to restrain the violent, primal, and anti-social tendencies of the id. Upon examination of the culpable individual, it will become evident that the superego has a defective framework. Freud expressed his need for punishment as a means to repress the inclination

to experience feelings of sinfulness and guilt in those who already feel guilty. According to Freud, these feelings originate from the oedipal era and are relegated to the subconscious mind. According to the psychoanalytic perspective, unsocial conduct might be attributed to the ongoing permissive behavior of both parents. In such a scenario, the child's superego is impaired, leading to incomplete development and an inability to regulate activities that are deemed unacceptable by society. As to Franz Alexander's concept, the guilty individual is someone who refuses to forgo immediate gratification and indulgence in order to get rewards in the future. The criminal is a person who fails to conform to societal norms due to an inability to adhere to the "reality principle". This concept, which should be acquired at the anal stage of development, namely during toilet training, is essential for establishing self-control and order in one's conduct. Alexander asserted that criminality is influenced not just by heredity and early experiences, but also by societal factors and family dynamics. Yochelson and Samenow argued that criminals had distinct cognitive patterns, which they referred to as "Ways of Thinking." However, they emphasized that although these patterns may be internally consistent, they are not morally justified. When individuals with early developed criminal thinking methods combine them with a feeling of irresponsibility in their disposition, it is expected for them to engage in criminal behavior.

The study has proven a correlation between crime and age. The inclination for solitary pursuits starts in educational establishments, peaks throughout the period between 20 and 40 years of age, and diminishes with advancing age (Dönmezer, 1981).

The transition from rural to urban areas, the shift from a traditional village economy to a market-based economy, uncontrolled urban growth, inadequate

development of the justice and penal system to address this situation, insufficient efforts to combat crime, leading to unemployment, erosion of traditional social order, cultural fragmentation, and the concentration of differences in a specific location. It is a primary factor contributing to crime rates in urban areas. Interest groups emerging in the industrial society endeavor to establish new regulations to safeguard their own interests. Thus, conflicts emerge over societal standards and principles. Consequently, there is a significant amount of variance from the standard. This circumstance significantly diminishes the harmonious cohabitation of the ecosystem. Nevertheless, by prioritizing the arrangement of the living environment, optimizing social and economic possibilities, and fostering public awareness, it is possible to mitigate the negative impact of industrial growth and achieve a harmonious industrial society that minimizes harm to the environment. Poor living circumstances, overcrowding, high crime and poverty rates in metropolitan areas, family separation, and the mother's pursuit of a career all contribute to the erosion of family cohesion. Consequently, the dissolution of cohesive and regulatory social groupings resulted in the deterioration of the social milieu. Lack of adaptability and noncompliance with new regulations in industrial settings diminishes environmental integration and exposes the primary factors contributing to criminal behavior.

Findings

Efficiently identifying and proactively preventing the underlying factors that contribute to criminal activities should be a paramount concern for many cultures. Crime is a pervasive issue seen in all communities.

Scientists from several disciplines, including Biology, Psychology, Law, Sociology, Political Science, and Economics, have drawn from diverse sources to articulate the underlying factors contributing to criminal behavior (Cömertler and Kar, 2007). These theories establish a connection between criminal conduct and biological, social, and psychological factors. They identify the fundamental causes of crime by considering socio-psychological and economical motives.

a) Sigmund Freud is the originator of this theorem, which establishes a connection between criminal behavior and the psychological condition. Freud posited that an individual's conduct is shaped by three components: the id, representing the primal self; the superego, representing the moral conscience; and the ego, representing the rational self. An imbalanced personality arises when there are various disturbances in the superego among these components. This scenario has a significant impact on the conduct of individuals, driving them towards engaging in criminal activities. Psychopathological conditions also manifest within this temporal interval.

b) According to the notion of biological determinism, criminals possess a distinct biological structure that sets them apart from the bulk of society. According to this discourse, criminality is believed to be a hereditary trait (Wolfgang, 1961).

The primary focus of the theory, which examines the social factors influencing criminal conduct, is attributed to Adolphe Quetelet, a Belgian statistician. As to his view, the environment is the catalyst for the crime, with the guilty individual only serving as a tool. Environmental variables are the underlying cause of criminal conduct in this instance.

d) According to the hypothesis positing that criminal conduct is driven by economic factors, the primary determinant of crime is the individual's income level. Raising one's economic level will diminish the inclination to engage in criminal activities due to the heightened opportunity cost associated with such behavior (Ehrlich, 1973).

e) According to socio-psychological theories of crime causation, crime is neither only attributed to exterior forces, as suggested by Quetelet, nor solely to interior elements, as indicated by Freud. Crime is a complex phenomenon that encompasses both social and psychological dimensions. In current legal systems, persons who perform activities recognized as crimes but lack awareness of the consequences or self-awareness are not considered criminals. Consequently, these persons are exempt from criminal penalties and are instead regarded as individuals afflicted with mental disorders. This persists till it is comprehended that it poses no threat to distinct persons. Hence, it is crucial to prioritize the examination of necrotic tissues while determining culpability.

It is advisable to enhance study efforts on this significant topic, which warrants comprehensive examination.

limitation

The limitations of the research are limited to the scope of the subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was conducted by limiting closely related authors and literature topics. Restricted to literature review.

Notifications

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial Support: The authors did not report any financial support related to this article.

Ethics Statement

Publication ethics of our university's relevant regulations; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to achieve this, aiming at these principles in the field of relevant sciences.

References

- Alexander, F., & Healy, W. (1935). *Roots of crime; psychoanalytic studies.*
- Alpman, P.S., & Yarci, S. (2018). Crime, migration and identity: the phenomenon of migration in crime theories. *Turkish Studies Social Sciences* , 13 (18), 143-158.
- Anderson, S. W., Bechara, A., Damasio, H., Tranel, D., & Damasio, A. R. (1999). Impairment of social and moral behavior related to early damage in human prefrontal cortex. *Nature Neuroscience*, 2, 1032-1037.
- Basile, B., Mancini, F., Macaluso, E., Caltagirone, C., Frackowiak, RS, and Bozzali, M. (2011). Deontological and Altruistic Guilt, Evidence for Distinct Neurobiological Substrates. *Human Brain Mapping*, 32, 229–239.
- Beccaria, C. (2009). *On crimes and punishments and other writings* . University of Toronto Press.
- Beccaria, C. (2016). *On crimes and punishments* . Transaction Publishers.
- Becker, H. S. (1963). *Outsiders* (Vol. 1973). New York: Free Press.
- Bentham, J. (1996). *The collected works of Jeremy Bentham: An introduction to the principles of morals and legislation* . Clarendon Press.
- Bernhardt, B.C., and Singer, T. (2012). The neural basis of empathy. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*, 35, 1–23.
- Besnard, P. (2017). The true nature of anomie. In *Emile Durkheim* (pp. 167-171). Routledge.
- Binder, A. (1988). Juvenile delinquency. *Annual review of psychology* , 39 (1), 253-282.
- Bingöl, I. (2022). A THEORETICAL APPROACH TO SOCIOLOGICAL CRIME THEORIES: SOCIAL PROCESS THEORIES. *Bingöl University Social Sciences Institute Journal (BUSBED)* , 12 (24), 640-652.
- Bonger, Willem: *Criminality and Economic Conditions*, abridged with an introduction by T. Turk, Austin, Bloomington-London, Indiana University Press, 1969.
- Buss, A. H., & Durkee, A. (1957). An inventory for evaluating different kinds of hostility in clinical situations. *Journal of Consulting Psychology*, 21, 343- 348.

- Castelli, F., Happé, F., Frith, U. and Frith, C. (2000). Movement and mind: a functional imaging study of perception and interpretation of complex intentional movement patterns. *NeuroImage*, 12(3), 314–325.
- COHEN, S., & TOPÇUOĞLU, T. (2014). The Failures of Criminology. *Journal of Penal Law and Criminology* , 2 (1-2), 269-280.
- CÖMERTLER, Necmiye and Muhsin KAR (2007), "SocioEconomic Determinants of Crime Rate in Turkey: Cross-Section Analysis", Ankara University, Political Sciences Faculty Journal, 62-2: 37-57.
- Çiçek, M. (2020). Aristotle's Concept of Justice. *Celal Bayar University Journal of Social Sciences* , 18 (04), 1-11.
- Daniel, A. E., Beck, N. C., Herath, A., Schmitz, M., & Menninger, K. (1984). Factors correlated with psychiatric recommendations of incompetency and insanity. *The Journal of Psychiatry & Law* , 12 (4), 527-544.
- De Montesquieu, C. (1989). *Montesquieu: The spirit of the laws* . Cambridge University Press.
- Decety, J. and Jackson, P. L. (2004). The functional architecture of human empathy. *Behavioral and Cognitive Neuroscience Reviews*, 3, 71– 100.
- Decety, J., Echols, S., and Correll, J. (2010). The blame game: the effect of responsibility and social stigma on empathy for pain. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 22, 985–997.
- Derryberry, D. and Tucker, D. M. (1991). The adaptive basis of the neural hierarchy: Elementary motivational controls on network function. *Nebraska Symposium on Motivation: Vol 38. Perspectives on motivation*, 38, 289-342.
- Dinç, AA (2022). *The concept of crime in classical utopias* (master's thesis, Trakya University Social Sciences Institute).
- Dönmezer S., (1981), *Criminology*, 6th Edition, Istanbul University Publication No: 2891, Faculty of Law No: 639, Istanbul.
- Dönmezer, S. (1948). Ecological Studies in Criminology. *Journal of Istanbul University Law Faculty* , 14 (3-4), 521-566.

- EHRlich, Isaac (1973), "Participation in Illegal Activities: A Theoretical and Empirical Investigation", *Journal of Political Economy*, 81: 521–65.
- Eisenberg, S., & Patterson, L. E. (1979). Helping clients with special concerns.
- Eysenck, H. J. (1984). Cattell and the theory of personality. *Multivariate Behavioral Research* , 19 (2-3), 323-336.
- Ferrajoli, L. (2019). Beccaria e Bentham. *Diciottesimo Secolo* , 4 , 75-84.
- Ferri, B., & Yin, L. (2022). The Distinct Roles of Poverty and Higher Earnings in Motivating Crime.
- Ferri, E. (2003). Causes of criminal behavior. *Criminological perspectives: Essential readings* , 52-57.
- Freud, S. (1989). The ego and the id (1923). *TACD Journal* , 17 (1), 5-22.
- Glueck, S., & Glueck, E. T. (1974). *Of delinquency and crime: A panorama of years of search and research* . Springfield, IL: C. C. Thomas.
- Gokulu, G. (2019). THEORIES OF CRIME: BIOLOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES: A CRITICAL EVALUATION. *Social Sciences* , 14 (4), 1471-1488.
- Greene, J.D., Sommerville, RB, Nystrom, LE, Darley, J.M., & Cohen, J.D. (2001). An fMRI investigation of emotional engagement in moral judgment. *Science*, 293, 2105–2108.
- Gruevska-Drakulevski, A. (2017). Labelling Theory-One of the Major Criminology Theories: Underlying Principles and Ideas, Main Assumed Mechanisms and Hypothesis, Critical Points. *Justinian Primus L. Rev.* , 8 , 1.
- Güdek, USK (2016). *Forensic social study of delinquency and criminal behavior* . Nobel Medical Bookstore.
- Gullu, I. (2014). A theoretical and critical approach to the phenomenon of crime. *Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University Journal of Social and Economic Research* , 2014 (3), 104-107.
- Hare, R. D. (1991). *The Hare psychopathy checklist – revised*. Toronto: Multi-Health Systems
- Healy, C. (2008). *Understanding your borderline personality disorder: a workbook* . John Wiley & Sons.

- Hooton, E. A. (1939). *Crime and the man*.
- Janssen, B., & Whiting, H. T. A. (1984). Sheldon's physical-psychical typology revisited. *Journal of Research in Personality* , 18 (4), 432-441.
- Kamer, V. K. (2013). SOCIOLOGICAL THEORIES REGARDING THE FACTORS THAT CAUSE CHILDREN TO DRIVE INTO CRIME. *Turkish Justice Academy Journal* , 4 (12).
- Karataş, Zeynep. "Examination of High School Students' Guilt and Shame Scores in Terms of Disciplinary Punishment and Gender". *Mersin University Faculty of Education Journal*, 4/2 (2008) 103-114.
- Latarjet, R. (1972). Antoine Lacassagne, 1884–1971.
- Lemert, E. (2014). Social pathology. In *Understanding Deviance* (pp. 173-179). Routledge.
- Lemert, E. M. (2000). *Crime and deviance: essays and innovations of Edwin M. Lemert* . Rowman & littlefield.
- Lombroso, C., Ferri, E., & Garofalo, R. (1886). *Polemica in difesa della scuola criminale positiva* . N. Zanichelli.
- Marchese di Beccaria, C. (1819). *An essay on crimes and punishments* (No. 47183). Philip H. Nicklin.
- Marx, K., & Engels, F. (1973). Karl Marx Friedrich Engels Werke. (*No Title*) .
- Marx, K., & Engels, F. (1975). *Marx & Engels Collected Works Vol 01: Marx: 1835-1843* . Lawrence & Wishart.
- Menninger, K. (1966). The Criminal Law System. *Neb. L. Rev.* , 45 , 22.
- Menninger, K. (1968). The crime of punishment.
- Menninger, K. A. (1986). Mental retardation and criminal responsibility: Some thoughts on the idiocy defense. *International journal of law and psychiatry* .
- Miller, H.V., & Miller, J.M. *Criminology and Social Science*.

- Newcomb, T. M. (1950). Role behaviors in the study of individual personality and of groups. *Journal of personality* .
- Öztürk, Özlem. Evaluation of Guilt-Shame Feelings in Adolescents Staying in Istanbul H Type Prison. Zonguldak: Karabük University Institute of Social Sciences, master's Thesis, 2005.
- Quetelet, A. (2003). Of the development of the propensity to crime. *Criminological perspectives essential readings* , 32-46.
- Reed, C. L., Shahom, S., Halgren, E., & Normann, R. (1999). Tactile object recognition activates the secondary somatosensory area (SII): an fMRI study. In *Soc Neurosci Abstr* (Vol. 25, p. 1894).
- Sellin, T. (2015). Culture conflict theory: The conflict of conduct norms. In *Criminology Theory* (pp. 71-75). Routledge.
- Shin, LM, Dougherty, DD, Orr, SP, Pitman, RK, Lasko, M., Macklin, ML, ...Rauch, SL (2000). Activation of anterior paralimbic structures during guilt-related script-driven imagery. *Biological Psychiatry*, 48(1), 43-50.
- Sığrı, Ünsal. et al. "Comparison of Feelings of Guilt and Shame in Employees According to Gender-Age Status and the Use of Shame Management in Organizations". *Cumhuriyet University Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 11/1 (2010) 71-85.
- Suominen, R., & Hakanurmi, S. (2013). *Verkko-opettaja* . Klaava Media.
- Sutherland, E. H., Cohen, A., Lindesmith, A., & Schuessler, K. (1956). The sutherland papers. *Trabajo y Derechos Humanos* , 133.
- Sykes, G. M. (1980). *The future of crime* . US Department of Health and Human Services, Public Health Service, Alcohol, Drug Abuse, and Mental Health Administration, National Institute of Mental Health, Center for Studies of Crime and Delinquency.
- ŞENOL, D., & SARIÇİÇEK, A. MURDER: A SOCIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF GENDER.
- Taft, M. (1994). Interactive activation as a framework for understanding morphological processing. *Language and cognitive processes* , 9 (3), 271-294.

- Tannebaum, R. D. (1996). Adult retropharyngeal abscess: a case report and review of the literature. *The Journal of emergency medicine* , 14 (2), 147-158.
- Tarde, G. (2010). *Gabriel Tarde on communication and social influence: Selected papers* . University of Chicago Press.
- Tomasi, L. (1993). Social differentiation and the current significance of Emile Durkheim's Anomie. *Social compass* , 40 (3), 363-374.
- Vold, G. B. (1958). *Theoretical criminology*.
- Wagner, U., N'Diaye, K., Ethofer, T., and Vuilleumier, P. (2011). Guilt-Specific processing in the Prefrontal Cortex. *Cerebral Cortex*, 21(11), 2461-2470.
- Wolfgang, M. E., Ferracuti, F., & Mannheim, H. (1967). *The subculture of violence: Towards an integrated theory in criminology* (Vol. 16). London: Tavistock Publications.
- WOLFGANG, Marvin (1961), "Pioneers in Criminology: Cesare Lombroso", *The Journal of Criminal Law, Criminology and Police Science*, 52, No.4: 1835-1909.
- Yochelson, S., & Samenow, S. E. (1977). *The criminal personality* Vo. 1 2: The change process. *New York: Jason Aronson* .
- Yochelson, S., & Samenow, S. E. (1994). *The criminal personality: The changing process* (Vol. 2). Rowman & Littlefield.